

EFFECT OF SEX SEPARATION ON GROWTH PERFORMANCE AND CARCASS CHARACTERISTICS OF BROILERS RAISED TO MATURITY

Sam, I.M., Akpa, G.N., ¹Alphonsus. C., G. I. Iyeghe-Erakpotobor and Agubosi O.C.P
Department of Animal Science, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

ABSTRACT

The effect of rearing method (mixed sex, separate males and separate females) on the growth characteristics of broiler birds was studied from day old to 18 weeks of age. Method of rearing had significant effect ($P<0.05$) on all the growth and performance characteristics (live weight, weight gain, and rate of increase in live weight and weight gain) studied. The mixed sex group had higher live weight and weight gain at 4 and 8 weeks of age but was overtaken by the male sex group at 12 and 18 weeks of age. Regardless of the rearing method, the live weight and weight gain of the birds increased at increasing rate from day old to 12 weeks of age, and then increased at decreasing rate to 18 weeks of age. The live weight increased at the rate of 85.83, 164.58, 219.44, and 190.74 g/bird/week at 4, 8, 12, and 18 weeks, respectively in the males sex group. While the increasing rate in the mixed sex group was 101.25, 170.83, 191.67, and 175.93g/bird/week at 4, 8, 12 and 18 weeks of age, respectively. The live weight increase in the female sex group was 84.83, 143.85, 177.75 and 155.70g/bird/week at 4, 8, 12 and 18 week of age, respectively. The effect of rearing method on the most economic parts of the broilers (breast weight, thigh weight and back weight) was significant ($P<0.05$) in all the sex groups except breast weight at 18 weeks and back weight at 4 and 8 weeks of age. This study therefore suggest that rearing of broilers from day old to 8 weeks of age might be economically beneficial when reared as mixed sexes rather than separate sexes

KEYWORDS: Broilers, rearing method mixed sex, separate male and separate female

INTRODUCTION

Broiler production offers the most rapid and cost effective means of making available high quality animal protein to man. In some areas of the world, Poultry meat is favoured over beef because of its higher protein and lower calorie content in addition to other favorable meat qualities such as tenderness (Dafwang, 2002). Modern broilers are the result of genetic selection, with the selection pressure being focused on high growth rate, extensive muscle development and relatively low feed consumption (Havestein *et al.*, 1994; Goliomytis *et al.*, 2003). These factors combine with improved environmental factors such as nutrition and housing have reduced the slaughter age of contemporary broiler chicken to 42 days and slaughter weight in excess of 2kg (Havestein *et al.*, 1994; Letterier *et al.*, 1998; Dafwang 2002). Most of the published works on broiler chickens are limited to between 32 and 63 days of age, living little or no information beyond this age on the overall growth potential of today's broiler chickens.

Differences in the growth rate of male and female broilers have been reported by many researchers (Laseinde and Oluyemi, 1994; Herry and Burke 1998; Rodenlli, 2005). However, there are few reports on the practice of separating broiler chicken into sexes while raising them. Laseinde and Oluyemi (1994) reported significant difference in body weight gain and feed intake between separated and mixed –sex –birds; while Verapeen and Driver (2000) reported significant benefits from rearing the broiler sexes separately. They reported that body weight gain and weight of most component carcass parts were significantly heavier in males than the females.

Male and female broilers have different growth potentials, which can be enhanced by management. For example, Meijerhof (1988) reported that male broilers utilized feed more efficiently than the female, the female broilers utilize dietary energy more efficiently than the males between week 5 and 8 of the growing period. From this report, there appear to be possible growth enhancing prospects in separating the sexes as a management practice. This prospect is one of the reasons that motivated this study. Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate the effect of sex separation on the performance characteristics of broiler chickens from day old to 18 weeks of age.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

The study was conducted in the poultry unit of Animal Science Department, Ahmadu Bello University, Samaru-Zaria. Located within the Northern Guinea Savannah zone of Nigeria, on latitude 11°12'N and Longitude 7°33'E, at an altitude of 610m above sea level. The climate is relatively dry, with a mean annual rainfall of 700-1400mm, occurring between the months of April and September. The dry season begins around the middle of October, with cold weather that ends in February. This is followed by relatively hot, dry weather from March to sometime in April, when the rain begins. The mean minimum and maximum daily temperature is from 14°C to 24°C during the cool season and from 19°C to 36°C during the hot season. The relative humidity varies between 19% and 35% in the dry season, and between 63% and 80% in the wet season. (Akpa 1999)

Experimental Birds and Management

Two hundred and seventy (270) Abor Acre breed of broiler chickens were purchased from Otta farm. The birds were identified and separated into three groups namely, males, females and mixed males and females using vent inspection method. Each bird was leg banded for individual identification. Each group was replicated thrice (30 birds per replicate) in a completely randomized design (CRD). The mixed group consisted of fifteen males and fifteen females per replicate. The birds were raised in deep litter system. They were uniformly fed standard diet *ad libitum* formulated to supply nutrient requirements according to NRC recommendation. The birds were individually weighed weekly using movable weigh scale.

Statistical analysis

The data collected was subjected to standard statistical analysis using general linear model (GLM) procedure of SAS,(2000) to find the effect of rearing method on live weight and weight gain of the broilers reared to 18 weeks of age. The model used was as follow:

$$Y_i = \mu + \alpha_i + \epsilon_i$$

Where: μ = overall mean

α_i = Effect of i^{th} rearing method (i: separate males, separate female, and mixed sex group)

ϵ_i = random error

RESULTS

The effect of rearing method on the overall performance characteristics of broiler birds is shown in Table 1. The effect of rearing method on the performance characteristics was significant on the feed intake, total weight gain and feed cost. The separate males consumed higher feed which invariably resulted in higher total weight gain than the separate females and mixed sex group.

The effect of rearing method on the external parts of the broilers was significant ($P < 0.05$) as shown in Table 2. The separate males had larger external body parts followed by the mixed sex group, while the females group had the least.

Table 3 shows the effect of rearing method on the live weight and weight gain of broilers at 4, 8, 12, and 18 weeks of age. Rearing method had significant ($P < 0.005$) effect on both the live weight and weight gain of the birds at 4, 8, 12 and 18 weeks of age. The mixed sex group had higher live weight and weight gain at 4 and 8 weeks of age, while the male sex group had higher live weight and weight gain at 12 and 18 weeks of age. The female's sex group generally had relatively lower live weight and weight gain than the female and mixed sex group in all the ages.

The effect of rearing method on the rate of increase in live weight and weight gain was significant ($P < 0.005$) at 8 and 12 weeks but not significant at 4 and 18 weeks of age. The live weight and weight gain of the birds was observed to increase at increasing rate from day old to 12 weeks of age, beyond this age the live weight and weight gain increased at decreasing rate to 18 weeks of age. However, the rate of increase in live weight and weight gain was higher in the mixed sex group up to 8 weeks, while the male sex group had higher rate of increase in live weight and weight gain at 12 weeks of age.

The effect of rearing method on the breast weight, thigh weight and back weight was significant ($P < 0.005$) in all the sex groups except breast weight at 18 weeks and back weight at 4 and 8 weeks of age Table 4. The male sex group had higher breast weight at 4, 8, and 12 weeks of age. The mixed sex group had higher thigh weight at 4

and 8 weeks of age, while the male sex group had higher thigh weight at 8, 12, and 18 weeks of age. The males' sex group had higher back weight at 12 and 18 weeks of age. The female sex group had the least breast weight, thigh weight and back weight in all the age categories.

DISCUSSION

The significant variation in feed intake of the broiler birds due to differences in rearing method in this study agrees with the earlier report of Varapeen and Driver (2000) and Rondelli (2005). The higher feed consumption of the separate males group had also been reported by Marks 1995 and Laseinde and Oluyemi (1996) that males broilers consumed more feed than the females of similar age. This could be attributed to the higher activity of the males than the females. Fischer (1985) reported that male birds are behaviorally more active than the females; hence consumed more feeds and gain weight faster than the females. The superiority of the males in the total weight gain agrees with Laseinde and Oluyemi (1994) who reported that male broilers grow faster and weigh heavier than the females under various rearing conditions.

The non significant difference in feed efficiency between the three sex groups indicates that feed efficiency is not affected by rearing method, this is in line with the earlier report of Laseinde and Oluyemi,(1994). The higher feed cost for the male sex group could be attributed to the relatively higher feed intake of the males, thus feed cost is dependent on feed intake of the birds.

The variation in the external parts of the birds due to differences in the rearing methods agrees with the earlier reports of Verapeen and Driver (2000). The male's external parts were relatively bigger and heavier than the other sex groups. This could be attributed to the higher growth rate of the males. However the higher weight of the head of the males than the females could be attributed to the presence of bigger comb and wattles in the males. Also the higher weight of the thigh and legs of the males is probably due to the greater ambulatory activities of the males within the deep litter system (Widowson,1980).

Effect of Rearing Method on Live Weight and Weight Gain of Broilers

Different live weight and weight gain of broilers at different ages have been reported by many authors (Laseinde and Oluyemi,1994; Varapeen and Driver, 2000; Goliomytis *et al*, 2003; Rondelli *et al* 2003 and Peters *et al* 2005). In this study, the live weight and weight gain of the mixed sex group was higher than the separate males and females group at 4 and 8 weeks of age. This indicates that the conventional rearing of broilers as mixed sex from 0 to 8 weeks of age is more economical than rearing them separate. However beyond the 8 weeks of age the males sex group had higher live weight and weight gain up to 12 weeks of age, this is probably due to the hormonal influence of androgen which is known to stimulate protein anabolism and increase nitrogen and mineral retention for growth and development (Iyeghe-Erakpotobor,2001). This observation suggests that rearing of male's broiler as separate sex up to 12 weeks of age might be beneficial. The live weight and weight gain of the broilers in this study increased with age regardless of the method of rearing, however the rate of the increase differs with age and rearing method. The live weight and weight gain in all the sex groups increased at an increasing rate from 4 to 12 weeks and beyond this age the live weight was increasing at decreasing rate to 18 weeks of age. The variations in the rate of increase in live weight and weight gain with rearing method had also been reported(Laseinde and Oluyemi, 1996;Verapeen and Driver 2000)

The rate of increase in live weight and weight gain was higher in the mixed sex group up to 8 weeks and was overtaken by the males sex group at the older ages. This indicates that rearing of broilers as mixed sex might be economical beneficial from day old to 8 weeks of age, beyond this the farmer may be running at a lost. However, rearing of the males broilers separately might be beneficial in terms of weight gain up to 12 weeks of age, probably due to the slow maturity rate of the males. This is inline with the report of Notter, (2003) that animals that are larger at maturity also takes longer time to reach mature weight, thus they mature more slowly and are less matured at any fixed chronological age or any fixed slaughter weight.

CONCLUSION

The result of this study suggests that there is no significant benefit in separating the broiler chickens into sexes during the eight weeks conventional period of rearing broilers. However when kept beyond 8 weeks, sex separation became useful because it enhanced better growth of separate birds, especially the males.

REFERENCES

- Akpa, G.N, Asiribo, E. O., Oni, O.O., Alawa, J. P., Dim, N.I., Osinowo, O. A., and Abubakar, B.Y. (2002). Milk production by Agropastoral Red Sokoto Goats in Nigeria. *Tropical Animal Health and Production*, 3, (6), 525 -533.
- Dafwang, I. I. (2002). Broilers and Broiler Production in Nigeria. In: *Poultry Production in Nigeria, A training manual of National Animal Production Research Institute*. Fed. Min. of Agric. And Rural Development ABU, Shika Zaria. Pp. 95 –108
- Fischer, G. J. (1985). The behaviour of chicken. In: *Bailliere Tindal*. Pp. 454-487.
- Gerald. Wiener, (1994). Animal breeding. *Tropical Agriculturalist CTA Macmillan London* PP. 11 – 12.
- Goliomytis, M., Panopoulou, Fand Regdakis, F (2003). Growth curves for body weight and major component parts, feed consumption and mortality of male broiler chicken raised to maturity. *Poult.Sci.*82:1061-1068
- Havestein, G.B., Ferket, P.R., Scheideler, S. E and Larson, B.T. (1994). Growth , Livability, and feed conversion of 1991 vs 1957 broilers when fed ' typical ' 1957 and 1991 vs 1957 broiler diets. *Poult. Sci.* 73: 1795 – 1084.
- Henry, M.H. and Burke, W. H. (1998). Sexual Dimorphism in Broiler chicks Embryos and Embryonic muscle Development in late incubation. *Poult. Sci.* 77:728 – 736.
- Iyeghe –Erakpotobor, G.T.(2001). Genetic,enviromental and nutritional influenceing growth and reproduction of rabbits in the semi-humid tropics. PhD Thesis Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. Pp.160
- Laseinde, E. A., and Oluyemi, J. A. (1994). Effect of sex separation at the Finisher phase on the comparative growth performance, carcass characteristics and breast muscle Development Between Male and Female Broiler Chicken. *Nig. Journal of Animal Production.* 21:11 –18.
- Laseinde, E. A., and Oluyemi, J.A. (1996).Sexual Dimorphism in the Growth Pattern of broilers under different dietary and housing conditions. *Nig. Journal of Animal Production* 24: 1 – 6.
- Lawrence, T.I.J. and V.R. Fowler (1998). Growth on farm animals. *CAB international* pp. 271 – 283.
- Latteier C., Rose, N., Costantin .P. and Nys, Y. (1998). Reducing growth rate of broiler chickens with a low energy diet does not improve cortical bone quality. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 39:24 –30
- Meijerhof, R. (1988). Separate sex feeding at the Dutch regional experimental poultry farms. *Proc. of 4th International poultry Breeders conf.* Pp 40 – 46
- Notter,P.P(2003). Evaluation of parameters needed to describe the overall growth, the chemical growth, and the growth of feathers and breast muscles of broilers. *Poult.Sci.* 78:812-821
- Peters,S.O., Ikeobi, O.C., OZOJE, M.O and Adebambo,O.A (2005). Modeling growth in seven chickens genotypes. *Nig. Journal of Animal Production.* 32(1):28-38
- Rondelli, S., Martinez, O. and Garcia, P. T. (2003).effect on productive parameters, carcass and bofy fat composition of two commercial broiler lines. *Rev. Bras. Cienc. Avic. Vol. 5 No. 3 compinas*
- SAS.1999. Statistical Analysis System Procedure guide for Personal computers. SAS Institute Inc.Cavy, North Carolina.
- Verapeen, D.S. and Driver, M. F. (2000). Separate sex growing of Ross 208 Broilers and effects on broiler performance and carcass quality. *Sci. and Tech. Research J.* 4:145- 152.
- Wilddowson, E. M. (1980). Definitions of growth. In *Growth in animals* (1980). Butterworths, London pp.

Table 5: effects of rearing method on some economic parts (gram) of broilers reared to 18 weeks of age

Rearing methods	breast (g/weeks)			
	4	8	12	18
	*	*	*	NS
Separate males	53.59 ^a	202.62 ^a	423.18 ^a	533.33
Mixed sex	42.20 ^b	214.07 ^a	380.74 ^{ab}	473.33
Separate females	38.62 ^c	171.06 ^b	340.28 ^b	476.67
SEM	1.85	15.79	21.61	35.31
	Thigh weight (g/weeks)			
	*	*	*	*
Separate males	63.92 ^b	305.97 ^a	602.39 ^a	790.00 ^a
Mixed sex	73.17 ^a	315.39 ^a	553.40 ^b	716.67 ^b
Separate females	64.19 ^b	262.44 ^b	426.00 ^c	650.00 ^b
SEM	3.90	8.90	19.48	35.50
	Back weight (g/week)			
	NS	NS	*	*
Separate males	50.22	184.21	399.98 ^a	523.33 ^a
Mixed sex	56.85	177.40	371.67 ^a	476.67 ^b
Separate females	48.57	177.82	295.44 ^b	433.33 ^c
SEM	4.73	13.72	15.47	18.18

*: P<0.005; a,b,c: means with different superscript within a column are significantly different (P<0.00)

Received for Publication: 20/07/2010

Accepted for Publication: 20/08/2010

Corresponding Author:

Alphonsus. C.,

Department of Animal Science, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Email: mcdyems@gmail.com